

BIOLOGICAL SCIENCES

GENETIC EVALUATION OF THALASSEMIA DISEASE IN AZERBAIJAN

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Abstract

Thalassemias are a genotypically and phenotypically heterogeneous group of diseases. There are β -, α -, δ -, $\delta\beta$ - and γ -thalassemias, of which β - and $\delta\beta$ -thalassemias are of greatest practical interest for Uzbekistan. β -thalassemia is the result of inhibition of beta-chain synthesis. In beta-thalassemia, there is an excess of alpha-polypeptide chains. Homozygous beta-thalassemia is characterized by the appearance of clinical signs in the second half of the first year of a child's life. Patients often die in the neonatal period, some survive to school age and adolescence. Beta-thalassemia is characterized by a Mongoloid face type, a tower-shaped skull, and delayed physical development. Pallor of the skin, icterus of the sclera, visible mucous membranes, hepatosplenomegaly and, due to this, an increase in the size of the abdomen are revealed.

Keywords: beta-thalassemia, blood transfusions, consanguineous marriage, Exjade, hemoglobinopathies.

Thalassemias are a heterogeneous group of blood diseases related to quantitative hemoglobinopathies, in which there is a decrease or complete absence of synthesis of globin chains that are part of the human hemoglobin molecule (HbA, HbP and HbA1c). Beta-thalassemia is based on hereditary inhibition of the synthesis of chains that are part of HbA. Beta-thalassemia is one of the most common hereditary diseases, it occurs in Southern Europe, especially often in the Mediterranean countries. In the territory of the former USSR, beta-thalassemia is widespread in the republics of Transcaucasia and Central Asia. In Georgia and Armenia, the carrier rate is about 3% [4, 6, 7]. The pathogenesis of thalassemia consists of a disruption of the synthesis of normal hemoglobin due to an excessive amount of free α - or β -chains of hemoglobin, which leads to the development of microcytic hypochromic anemia. Excess α -chains in homozygous beta-thalassemia quickly precipitate and form insoluble inclusions in bone marrow normoblasts, destroying them, which leads to the development of ineffective erythropoiesis and bone marrow hyperplasia. Precipitates in reticulocytes and mature erythrocytes are removed in the spleen, while the erythrocyte membrane is damaged and its permeability for cations increases, as a result, the lifespan of erythrocytes is reduced and hemolysis develops. Expressed erythroid hyperplasia is the main cause of excessive hematopoiesis in the bones, which causes their deformation. Often, foci of red hematopoiesis are found in the liver and spleen. Ineffective erythropoiesis induces increased iron absorption, leading to pathological iron overload.

The main clinical signs of the disease are microcytic hypochromic anemia, delayed physical and sexual development, hepatosplenomegaly, changes in the bones of the skull, and iron overload [8, 9]. Major beta-thalassemia, or Cooley's anemia, is a severe form of progressive hemolytic anemia that requires constant blood transfusions.

Despite the lack of reliable information regarding the situation in many regions of the world, according to the latest data, about 7% of the world's population are

carriers of genes for hemoglobin disorders. Today, hemoglobinopathies are not limited to any particular region; they are widespread diseases throughout the world and represent a global public health problem. Hemoglobinopathies have spread due to population migration from endemic areas to countries where they were extremely rare among the native population.

The intermediate form of beta-thalassemia is similar in symptoms to beta-thalassemia major, but all symptoms are expressed much weaker. Such patients survive to adulthood and can have offspring. Clinical manifestations of hemosiderosis are expressed much less and appear 10-20 years later than in thalassemia major. The main cause of death in these patients is heart failure. Clinical manifestations of the minor form of beta-thalassemia are very insignificant [2, 6, 7]. Patients complain of rapid fatigue, weakness after physical exertion, decreased hemoglobin content during intercurrent diseases. A slight enlargement of the spleen and slight bilirubinemia (due to the indirect fraction) are often observed. In women, the above symptoms sometimes appear only during pregnancy. The clinical significance of this form of thalassemia is that it aggravates the course of acute and chronic diseases, pregnancy and is often accompanied by folate deficiency [6, 8]. The minimal form of beta-thalassemia is asymptomatic carriage of the thalassemia gene, diagnosed only by laboratory methods (the most reliable is the DNA test) [6]. The diagnosis of thalassemia should be assumed if the patient has microcytic hypochromic anemia with normal or elevated serum iron levels [1]. All forms of thalassemia are characterized by a decrease in quantitative erythrocyte indices: mean corpuscular volume (MCV), mean corpuscular hemoglobin content (MCH), mean corpuscular hemoglobin concentration (MCHC). A normal or slightly elevated level of the erythrocyte distribution width (EDW) is usually observed in heterozygotes for the beta-thalassemia gene, while in homozygotes this indicator is significantly higher than normal [3, 5]. The hemoglobin content in major thalassemia does not exceed 40-50 g/l, in intermediate thalassemia it fluctuates within 60-80

g/l, and in minor and minimal forms within 90-120 g/l. The osmotic resistance of erythrocytes is increased, 100% hemolysis occurs in a 0.25-0.15% solution of NaCl, and in rare cases only in distilled water.

Thalassemia is characterized by characteristic changes in the clinical blood test. The number of red blood cells, the level of hemoglobin (in severe forms - sometimes up to 20-30 g / l) and the color index are sharply reduced. Red blood cells are of reduced size, often of an unusual appearance - the so-called "target-shaped". For diagnosis, it is also useful to use the results of a biochemical blood test and, possibly, an analysis of a bone marrow sample. Analysis of hemoglobin by electrophoresis, as well as biochemical determination of fetal hemoglobin can confirm the diagnosis. In thalassemia, the amount of "normal" hemoglobin is reduced, but the amount of abnormal is increased. It is useful to collect a family history to establish the hereditary nature of anemia. In some cases, genetic analysis can be carried out to identify a specific genetic defect. One of the most important pathological processes that determine the course of hemoglobinopathies is the excessive accumulation of iron in the body, which is caused by its insufficient absorption by bone marrow cells, as well as increased absorption in the gastrointestinal tract [5]. Процесс накопления избытка железа существенно возрастает при переливаниях эритроцитной массы. Развивается гемосидероз внутренних органов. В наибольшей степени страдают сердце, печень, кожа, а также железы внутренней секреции, в частности, поджелудочная железа [6,12].

All forms of thalassemia are characterized by the presence of "target" erythrocytes in the blood, in which hemoglobin is located in the center of the cell as a target. Due to chronic anemia, the bone marrow is in a state of hyperregeneration, which gradually leads to the typical deformation of flat bones. Long-term oxygen starvation leads to a lag in the child's physical development. During adolescence, sexual development also slows down. Neuropsychic development does not suffer. Diagnostics of hemoglobinopathies is rapidly improving. In the 70s of the last century, hemoglobin electrophoresis began to be widely used, which determines the insufficiently synthesized Hb chain (α, β, γ, δ, or their combination) and the amount of normal adult HbA. In the 80s, DNA research began. Since the 90s, a tendency has been noted to use mRNA for a more detailed study of the molecular basis of hemoglobinopathies. Molecular diagnostics are performed depending on the mutation responsible for the synthesis of the defective globin chain, and when examining the DNA or RNA of the parents, it is possible to determine the type of inheritance (homozygous, heterozygous, double heterozygous (by one allele) and compound heterozygous (by different alleles). Currently, more than 200 β-thalassemic and more than 50 α-thalassemic mutations are known.

Diagnostics of α-thalassemia requires molecular biological studies, since electrophoresis may be inconclusive. Suspicion of α-thalassemia

arises with clinical and laboratory signs of the disease and the absence of changes in hemoglobin electrophoresis [7,10,11].

Necessary measures and tests that must be carried out to determine the disease:

- A complete blood count with platelet count, white blood cell count, reticulocytes and normoblasts (young nucleated red blood cells, normally absent from peripheral blood), which will allow the doctor to assess how adequately the treatment of a clinically significant form of thalassemia is organized.

- A biochemical blood test with an assessment of liver and kidney function, iron stores in the body (serum ferritin) allows you to assess the safety of the therapy being administered to you (your child).

- Ultrasound of the abdominal organs and retroperitoneal space - necessary for 15 assessment of the size of the liver, spleen and kidneys, early detection of gallstones and pseudotumor masses of extramedullary hematopoiesis.

- A study of cardiac function (ECHO-CG and ECG, if necessary, daily ECG monitoring) for all patients with clinically significant forms of thalassemia from the moment of diagnosis and then annually.

- Hormonal profile study for all transfusion-dependent patients over 8 years of age.

- Iron content in the liver, myocardium and pituitary gland before the start of chelation therapy and to monitor the release of excess iron from the organs.

- Screening for infections transmitted by components of donor blood (HIV, hepatitis B and C) in the case of regular transfusions - monthly, in rare transfusions - annually [8].

- Assessment of visual acuity and hearing before the start of chelation therapy and then annually. Assessment of bone mineral density of the skeleton annually starting from adolescence.

There are more than 1 million carriers of thalassemia in Azerbaijan. Carriers are not sick, they differ little from healthy people. Currently, more than 3,000 hereditary blood diseases, including thalassemia, are registered in the country. The Decree "On state assistance to persons with hereditary blood diseases hemophilia and thalassemia" was prepared in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Azerbaijan dated July 18, 2005 No. 264 "On the application of the Law of the Republic of Azerbaijan".

As of 01.01.2020, the number of patients with hemoglobinopathy (ph-thalassemia, α-thalassemia, drepanothalassemia, sickle cell anemia and other hemoglobinopathies) registered in the thalassemia department of the National Center for Hematology and Transfusiology is 3414 people. About 35% of these patients (1080 people) are from Baku (Absheron, Gobustan, Shamakhi). The distribution among other cities is as follows: Sumgait - 97, Nakhchivan - 27, Ganja - 162, Sheki - 634, Mingachevir - 593, Guba - 107, Shirvan - 347, Lankaran - 198, Barda - 169 people.

STATISTICS OF PATIENTS WITH THALASSEMIA

Major form in thalassemia 1289 blood recipients: 1008

Intermediate form in thalassemia 597 blood recipients: 142

Minor form in thalassemia 721 blood recipients: 0

Considering the high frequency of inbreeding in some regions of Azerbaijan, homozygotization of each pathological gene separately occurs, as well as the emergence of their new combinations. All this complicates not only the diagnosis, but also the treatment of homozygous states of thalassemia. However, identifying the features of the population-genetic characteristics of the population, compiling a genogeographic map of mutations, compiling a register and an information base will improve the quality of premarital and prospective medical-genetic counseling.

In addition, these studies will contribute to the introduction of transplantation practices, including stem cells, for thalassemia, which is not currently carried out in Azerbaijan. Educational work among the population, the introduction and development of express methods and diagnostic tests for screening thalassemia during pregnancy, prenatal diagnosis of the fetus, in newborns, applied in the work of medical genetic counseling, will allow the development of a concept for their prevention.

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